

A Note on Covert Channel Amplification for Time-decoupled Secret Message Exchanges

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1 Introduction and threat scenario

A covert channel is a policy-breaking and usually stealthy communication channel. In [1], we describe a method to covertly exchange secret data by embedding the data into commercial off-the-shelf Internet of Things (IoT) devices, such as printers or smart speakers. A core goal of that paper is to realize a *time-decoupled* secret data exchange (Fig. 1): Alice wants to covertly transmit data to Bob. However, an adversary should not be able to observe Alice and Bob accessing the same storage location simultaneously. To this end, Alice must embed secret information at some point in time while Bob retrieves the information later, e.g., one hour after Alice hid the message. For example, whistleblower Alice and journalist Bob could visit the same café that (unintentionally) provides some accessible smart speaker through the local guest WiFi. Alice hides secret data on the device’s cache at morning, and then leaves the café. Bob appears in the afternoon or the following day to retrieve the data. An observer would never see Alice and Bob at the same time.

Figure 1: Time-decoupled exchange of secret information as in [1].

*The author is with the University of Ulm, see www.wendzel.de for contact details. This document serves as an electronic supplement for [1]. Moreover, it can be considered an additional electronic supplement for [2].

Problem statement While [1] describes technical details on how data can be hidden in the IoT devices, the amount of data that can be stored on a device is usually just a few hundred bytes. This document explains how the amount of covert data can be increased by amplifying the size of the covert message.

2 Covert channel amplification

As explained, Alice and Bob de-couple their secret exchanges. This also means that they will transfer only few messages per day and all of these messages are limited by the maximum storage space $s_{max}(d)$ provided by the IoT device d (see [1] for details). For this reason, they must exchange as much data as possible per message.

Core idea Alice and Bob apply covert channel amplification (introduced in [2]), i.e., they amplify the secret message size using pointers to *volatile* data. Among other advantages, volatile data allows Alice to use a timing pointer that can be smaller than the data being pointed to [2], i.e., Alice can even point to uniformly distributed data.¹

Amplification procedure Instead of directly embedding the secret message M , Alice embeds a single reference (called “pointer”) r_1 or a set of concatenated pointers $r_1||\dots||r_n$ of summarized length $\sum |r_i| = |M|$ ($|x|$ being the string length of x). Each pointer r_i refers to a message fragment f_i found elsewhere (e.g., an address location within the IoT device’s memory). Note that if the fragments are *static*, one could consider this approach to use a “code book”. In contrast to a classic code book, the fragments used for covert channel amplification are *volatile* [2], i.e., fragments refer to an ephemeral secret message that could not be reconstructed by an adversary who gains ex post access.

Alice ensures that $\sum |r_i| \leq s_{max}(d)$, i.e., the concatenated pointers fit into the provided space of device d . To achieve an amplification, Alice ensures that the condition (1) is met:

$$\sum |f_i| > \sum |r_i|. \tag{1}$$

However, Alice’s goal is to transfer more data to Bob as is possible to hide in the IoT device ($s_{max}(d)$). To this end, Alice ensures that $\sum |f_i| > s_{max}(d)$ (this reflects the general idea of [2], where the gained increase in covert message size is called the *covert amplification factor*, CAF).

A note on insufficient pointers Previous work did not analyze message fragmentation. Only DYST [2] had a setting where multiple pointers were

¹Pointing to uniformly distributed data would not permit an amplification using non-volatile (i.e., *static*) data as the pointer’s size would be required to be as large as the data being pointed to.

combined during embedding. It was implicitly assumed that $\forall i : f_i > r_i$. However, if $\forall i : |f_i| \geq |r_i|$, Alice can still achieve an amplification of the message size because the combined length of the messages referred to can still be longer than the message M itself if condition (1) is met (as long as at least one pointer achieves an increase of the message size).

Finally, an amplification can be reached if $\exists i : f_i < r_i$, i.e., a pointer (or even multiple pointers) can refer to a fragment that has a *shorter* length than the particular pointer. However, this is only true as long as condition (1) is still met, i.e., when other pointers remedy the effect of such an “insufficient” pointer.

Volatility As mentioned above, a general advantage of covert channel amplification is the idea to point to volatile data, which renders the approach different from a code book and allows an amplification even when referring to uniformly distributed data. Alice and Bob might refer to a current event or time-dependent data such as some kind of notification or status inside the IoT device or outside of it.²

Due to the ephemeral nature of the fragments in time-decoupled transmissions, one must take into account the expected lifespan of a fragment. Without decreasing the CAF, a message can only be received in its entirety if *all* fragments are still accessible by Bob at the time of retrieval.³ One option to *control* the lifetime of fragments being pointed to is to refer to data that Bob can overwrite after retrieving the message. For instance, Alice might refer to memory segments that are static until a trigger (such as a specific loading attempt to a web interface hosted on the IoT device) causes a data replacement in these segments, which could be triggered by Bob.

References

- [1] WENDZEL, S. AdullamoT: Using IoT devices as relays for time-decoupled secret exchange & censorship circumvention. In *Proc. 14th ACM Workshop on Information Hiding and Multimedia Security (IH&MMSec’26)* (2026), ACM.
- [2] WENDZEL, S., SCHMIDBAUER, T., ZILLIEN, S., AND KELLER, J. DYST (Did you see that?): An amplified covert channel that points to previously seen data. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing (TDSC)* 22, 1 (2025), 614–631.

²In our previous work, we implemented covert channel amplification by referencing volatile network traffic that did not bring the constraints of time-decoupled transmissions [2]. In other work, we used website content, flow-based characteristics and payload. See <https://wendzel.de/misc/2026/02/28/history-cc.html> for a summary.

³While error-correcting codes could be applied to handle corrupted or lost messages as in case of DYST-EXT, it would require to use a fraction of the available space to embed redundant/error-correcting information [2].